

Introduction of Information System Analysis and Design

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Abstract—The development of information technology is currently running fast and a lot. There are many advantages that can be obtained from the development of information technology. For example, in the business sector, information technology can be used to improve promotions and to assist the processing of existing data for used as information. For processing data into information, one of the examples are data processing or transactions of a purchase or sale, where by processing the data using a computer, the processing will be faster and the results are much better than doing without using a computer (Rumanta, 2013: 44-49).

Index Terms— System, Information, Technology, Industry, Design

I. INTRODUCTION

An information system is a man-made system consisting of components within the organization to be able to present information. A good information system can improve the performance of all activities within the company that are supported by accurate and secure data, so that all activities can run more effectively. The effectiveness and efficiency of information systems is a key aspect that can determine the progress or decline of an organization. Manufacturing industry organizations can not be separated from it. An effective and properly implemented information system will affect the performance of management in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry. However, information systems that are too complex and complicated can reduce the efficiency of the overall production system. Web-based applications are often used to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of a process. Examples of its application are quite broad, such as to improve the efficiency of the learning process, consumption of electrical energy at home. and the survey data collection process. Increased efficiency This occurs because web-based applications make it easier for actors involved in the system to carry out their duties.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of System

There are many definitions of the system put forward by experts. In this case the author tries to put forward a system definition that is quite logically acceptable, namely: The system can be interpreted as a collection or set of elements or variables that are mutually organized, interact with each other,

and depend on each other. According to Mc. Leod (1995) defines the system as a group of elements that are integrated with the same intent to achieve a goal. According to Scott (1996) the system consists of elements such as input (input), processing (processing), and output (output). From the three definitions of the system above, the author concludes that the system is an element that is interconnected with each other to achieve a certain goal.

The definition of an information system can be derived based on definition of each of the constituent words, namely system and information. Anggraini and Zega defined the system as a collection of several elements or elements that are mutually interact to achieve a certain goal. Definition

The same thing was also given by Jogiyanto who explained that: system as a network of interconnected work for perform an activity or complete a specific goal. The system can be a group of people, machines, things or types other entities.

B. Definition of Information

Information is data that is processed into a form that is more useful and more meaningful to those who receive it. The source of information is data. Data is a fact that describes an event and a real entity. An event is something that happens at a certain time.

C. Definition of System Information

According to Robert A. Leitch and K. Roscoe Davis, an information system is a system within an organization that brings together the daily transaction processing needs, supports operations, is managerial and strategic activities of an organization and provides certain outside parties with the necessary reports.

Leitch and Davis defines an information system as a system that connects the daily transaction processing needs, support operations, management activities and strategies within a organization to provide the required reports, both for internal and external purposes.

The purpose of information systems in general is to provide information that can help in making management decisions, facilitate the implementation of daily activities and provide complete information to third parties, especially on the issue of transparency in management.

One technique for device improvement in an records device is SDLC(System Development Life Cycle). SDLC is a conventional method had to broaden, maintain, and update records structures. SDLC is the manner of creating and

converting the device and the version and method used to broaden those structures. SDLC is likewise a sample taken to broaden a software program device such as levels particularly, making plans, analysis, design implementation, and maintenance. Some of the blessings of enforcing SDLC, particularly SDLC can assist with accurate assignment making plans, estimation, and scheduling; Project manipulate may be executed extra easily, all stakeholders can understand how the software program improvement cycle transparently; can pace up the software development process; lessen assignment risk; can lessen assignment control prices and manufacturing prices; and enhance accurate relationships with clients. In software program engineering, the idea of SDLC underlies one of a kind forms of software program improvement methodologies.

D. Information Database Design

Information system design is the development of a new system from the existing old system, where the problems that occur in the old system are expected to be resolved in the new system.

Database design is a process that produces a detailed data model of the database, database design involves selecting: columns for each table and how tables and columns interact with each other. Term database design can function as an application of the whole design process, not just the structure database, but also queries and forms that have functions as part of the overall database within a database management system.

E. Analysis

The development team considers the functional requirements of the system to assess how the solution will meet end-user expectations. The purpose of this phase is to understand the business requirements and processing of information systems projects. System analysis is a stage carried out with various activities, including conducting a literature review to find cases that can be handled by the system, classifying problems, opportunities and solutions that can be applied to these cases, analyzing system requirements and making boundaries, defining system requirements. End user requirements are defined and documented and usually a feasibility study is conducted to determine whether a project is feasible from a financial, organizational, social and technological point of view.

III. DISCUSSION

The development of information systems in laboratory processes is more focused on improving system efficiency. This laboratory uses the traditional SDLC method development which uses traditional methods to develop, maintain, and replace information systems.

A. Analysis System Information

The actual information system applied to the Laboratory Process IV includes several activities, including: testing samples using X-ray and QCX machines, data processing

using spreadsheet software and reporting results to evaluation staff and Central Control Panel (CCP) operators.

Another issue that needs attention is the possibility fraud committed by actors in the system. Standards and formulations set by the evaluation staff stored in the form of conditional functions and spreadsheets the standard does not provide a security system for these features. This condition allows all actors in the system to modify existing standard and conditional functions.

B. Design System Information

Use case diagrams are formed based on all use cases and actors involved in system. The results of the identification of use cases and system actors that. The requirements for the proposal system are as follows:

1. Use Case

The use of the proposed information system is:

- a. Login.
- b. Defining and changing operator level.
- c. Defining and changing parameter values and standard.
- d. Input oxide percentage data.
- e. Data input conditions and operational limits.
- f. Access daily reports.
- g. Access monthly reports.
- h. Access data set points.

2. Actor

Various actors involved in the proposed information system among others:

- (a) Admin, is an actor who plays a role as application controller. Have the authority to define and change quality standards, parameters and user level;
- (b) Operator 1, has the authority to input data and access daily reports;
- (c) Staff Evaluation, has authority to access reports daily, monthly, QAF and other types of reports; and
- (d) CCP operators, are actors in the department other and is considered an outside party but requires the output of the system. CCP operators are only allowed to access data set points only.

The last stage in the design of information systems is database creation. Database designed based on ERD and created using the local XAMPP server.

C. Design Web Based Application

Web-based application design aims to support implementation of the proposed information system. The plan are as follows:

1. Log In Pages

The design of the log in pages

2. Home Pages

The designed web-based application has three different home page views. Third view adjusted to the level of users who

access the application. There is a home page for operators, evaluation staff and CCP operators.

3. Admin Pages

The features available in the admin pages are buttons for change parameters and values of quality standards as well as page to change user level.

4. Input Pages

Input pages can only be accessed by the operator. Page for operational conditions and limitations.

5. Report Pages

There are two types of reports: the usual Daily Report called LHK and the Monthly Report commonly called LPB. An example of LHK, while an example of LPB. Display features graph of the data contained in the report as well added to the application and accessed by the evaluation staff. amp example

IV. CONCLUSION

Preliminary study of based information systems spreadsheet used in the Process Laboratory IV PT X shows that there are still some weaknesses such as: slow flow of information, lack of security information, as well as the potential for various forms of fraud. This research was conducted to design a system more efficient information through the implementation of -based applications web. The results of the design involve four actors with the authority and different levels of access. The difference will improve information security, so that various forms of fraud involving the manipulation of data by another party can be minimized. In addition, the design of information systems also eliminating repetitive set point data input activities usually carried out by Operator 1. Eliminate the activity reduce the time required to implement the whole process, thereby increasing efficiency system. In addition, loop elimination also minimizes potential the occurrence of human errors and writing errors in the process input data. Based on this, it can be concluded that the design of information systems with web-based applications has been able to help increase efficiency and minimize weaknesses of existing information systems in the Process Laboratory IV PT at this time. Further research can be directed at two levels: (1) At more limited level, information system design capabilities with a web-based application at PT X's IV Process Laboratory can be further developed so that it becomes Decision Support System (DSS); or (2) At a higher level broadly, the application of information system design with applications web-based can be expanded to cover all Process Laboratory at PT. X. It can be impetus for the development of quality control systems intranet based.

V. REFERENCES

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